
Lethality of Opioid Overdose in a Community Cohort of Young Heroin Users

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Key Words

Heroin users · Opioid overdose · Mortality · Lethality

Abstract

Background: The aim of the study was to estimate the lethality of opioid overdose among young heroin users. **Methods:** A prospective community cohort study was conducted in Barcelona and Madrid, Spain. Participants included 791 heroin users aged 18–30 years who were followed up between 2001 and 2006. Fatal overdoses were identified by record linkage of the cohort with the general mortality register, while non-fatal overdoses were self-reported at base-line and follow-up interviews. The person-years (py) at risk were computed for each participant. Fatal and non-fatal overdose rates were estimated by city. Transition towards injection shortly before the overdose could not be measured. Overdose lethality (rate of fatal overdose in proportion to total overdose) and its 95% CI was estimated using Bayesian models. **Results:** The adjusted rates of fatal and non-fatal opioid overdose were 0.7/100 py (95% CI: 0.4–1.1) and 15.8/100 py (95% CI: 14.3–17.6), respectively. The adjusted lethality was 4.2% (95% CI: 2.5–6.5). **Conclusions:** Four out of 100 opioid overdoses are fatal. These are preventable deaths that could be avoided before or after the overdose takes place. Resources are urgently needed to prevent fatal opioid overdose.

Introduction

Heroin and other illicit opioids – either prescribed but illicitly obtained or illicitly produced – are still the illicit substances that account for most drug-related deaths, both in the European Union and worldwide [1]. Annual mortality among opioid users has been estimated at 2.1

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per 100 person-years (py) [2], which is 10–20 times higher than among their peers in the general population [2, 3]. During the 1990s all-cause mortality among opioid users in Barcelona reached 3.5 deaths per 100 py [4, 5], and in 1999 standardized opioid overdose mortality in the city was 0.5 per 100 py [6]. The decline in mortality was probably due mainly to a decrease in heroin use, drug injection and HIV infection among drug injectors [7, 8]. Nevertheless, the European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA) states that overdose continues to be a major cause of death in 2013, especially among young people, accounting for approximately 4% of all deaths in adult males under 40 years of age [9], with significant heterogeneity in overdose mortality rates between European countries [10]. Non-fatal overdoses among opioid users are much more common than fatal overdoses, with an annual prevalence of 9–22% [11–13].

Various kinds of intervention have been implemented worldwide to prevent opioid overdose, with the aim of reducing the risk of overdose and also of death following overdose [9, 14]. On the one hand, one group of interventions is focused on avoiding risk behaviours such as use of the injected route of administration, opioid use after a long abstinence, concurrent use of other central nervous system depressants, etc. [9, 15]. In addition, a second group of interventions is focused on avoiding opioid use in solitary or ‘behind closed doors’, such as by implementing supervised drug consumption rooms and providing prompt and proper attention to those affected by an overdose, e.g. distribution of naloxone to opioid users or their relatives [9, 14].

Several countries routinely publish information about overall opioid overdose deaths in the population and among cohorts of opioid users. This information may facilitate assessment of the effectiveness of interventions aimed at preventing overall opioid overdose deaths. However, it is not appropriate for assessing the effectiveness of measures specifically aimed at preventing death following an overdose. To evaluate these measures, it is necessary to obtain estimates of the lethality of opioid overdose, i.e. the proportion of opioid overdoses in which the affected person dies. Despite its importance, little information on this indicator is available because it is very complicated to obtain reliable data. As far as we are aware, this indicator has only been estimated in Australia (5.0% in 1994 [12], and thereafter 3.1–4.1% [16]) and in Scotland (3.8% [17]). Therefore, the aim of this study was to estimate the lethality of opioid overdose among young heroin users in Barcelona and Madrid, Spain.

Methods

We analysed data from a prospective cohort study (The ITI-NERE Project) of young heroin users. The main methodological details of the cohort have been reported elsewhere [18]. The cohort were from the cities of Barcelona and Madrid, which were mainly chosen to cover the two basic epidemiological profiles related to the route of heroin administration in Spain: Barcelona, where injection was predominant, and Madrid, where a transition had occurred on the route of heroin administration (mainly towards smoking) and injection was no longer predominant. Participants were street-recruited from 2001 to 2003 ($n = 791$) by snowball sampling methods in each city. Recruitment in drug treatment centres was avoided. Up to a maximum of three computer-assisted personal interviews using a pre-coded questionnaire were scheduled at 12-month intervals, and took place in health and social centres (medical or nursing consultations, social work departments, neighbourhood or district centres, etc.).

Participants were asked about the number of opioid overdoses suffered during the 12 months prior to baseline and between follow-up visits [19], and 66.5% of the subjects provided current information on the number of overdoses during follow-up. Data on non-fatal overdose from baseline and follow-up visits was pooled because there was a statistical non-significant difference in the rate of non-fatal overdose between participants who only gave information at baseline (18 per 100 py) and those who updated their information during follow-up (16 per 100 py). A non-fatal opioid overdose was precisely defined in the questionnaire as ‘an episode occurring after opioid use (heroin, methadone, or other opioids such as “buprex”, “sosegon”, “deprancol”, or “morphine”), and characterized by extreme difficulty in breathing, loss of consciousness and problems waking up or recovering consciousness, and possibly bluish skin or lips’, in the 12 months prior to the interview. The following clarification was also included, ‘Please keep in mind that we are not interested in overdoses due to cocaine, amphetamines or ecstasy, which are usually accompanied by hot flushed skin or fever, tachycardia, nervousness, anxiety and sometimes convulsions’.

Data on fatal opioid overdoses were obtained by linking all community cohort subjects to the National Mortality Register from the National Statistics Institute, up to December 2006. In order to identify deaths from opioid overdose, we used codes from the 10th revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10), proposed by EMCDDA (F11, F12, F14–F16, F19, X42, X62, Y12) [20], plus codes X44 and X49, which are often used in Spain to signify overdose deaths not classifiable under any other code [21]. Participants not detected as deceased were considered to be alive at the end of the study period (December 31, 2006). In Barcelona a cross-validation of fatal opioid overdoses with a special register of the Legal Medicine Institute was carried out. Participants gave informed consent, and the study design was approved by the Bioethics Committee Review Board of Instituto de Salud Carlos III.

Analysis

The annual fatal opioid overdose rate (FOR) and non-fatal opioid overdose rate (NOR), as well as overdose lethality (OL) with corresponding 95% CI were estimated using Bayesian models. It was assumed that the numbers of both fatal and non-fatal opioid overdoses would follow binomial distributions. Moreover, FOR

and NOR follow a vague prior beta distribution (0.5, 0.5). FOR and NOR were estimated by dividing the number of overdose episodes (which could be more than 1 NOR per person) by the total number of person-years (py) at risk during follow-up, and OL was estimated as the proportion given by $[\text{FOR}/(\text{FOR} + \text{NOR})] \times 100$, using a measure of central tendency of the posterior distribution (the median) and its 95% CI. This distribution was obtained using Monte Carlo methods based on Markov chains with the Gibbs sampling algorithm, run through 400,000 iterations, and discarding the first 40,000 as burn-in. Finally, a thin of 360 was specified, meaning that an iteration of every 360 was stored. The convergence criterion was assessed as proposed by Gelman et al. [22]. The data were analysed using WinBUGS version 1.4.1.

Since Madrid and Barcelona had different profiles of heroin users, especially in terms of the use of injection as a drug administration route [23], crude FOR, NOR and OL were calculated for each city. Moreover, to determine the lethality ratio independently of sex, age group, educational level, treatment and drug injection status at baseline, we calculated FOR, NOR and OL after adjustment for all of these variables. Finally, for individuals for whom we had up-to-date information about changes in administration route during follow-up, we calculated FOR, NOR and OL according to their status during this period: (1) injectors during follow-up, (2) non-injectors during follow-up and (3) participants who changed administration route, i.e. non-injectors at baseline who were injecting at follow-up, and injectors at baseline who were non-injectors at follow-up.

Results

The proportion of participants aged 18–25 years and drug users who had been drug injectors at some point during their lifetime was much higher in Barcelona than in Madrid. In Barcelona, 53.3% of heroin users were younger than 26 years of age and 80.5% had been injectors once in their lifetime, while in Madrid these percentages were 32.8 and 65.1%, respectively (table 1). Approximately 4.9 and 3.6% of the subjects in Barcelona and Madrid, respectively, lived alone during most of the recall period. Total follow-up time was 2,435 py. Seventeen of 791 young heroin users died during follow-up. Table 2 shows crude and adjusted FOR and NOR, and the adjusted OL ratio among young heroin users. While there were no statistically significant differences in unadjusted or adjusted FOR between Barcelona and Madrid (although the point estimate was higher in Barcelona), there were statistically significant differences in unadjusted NOR between Barcelona [30.4 (95% CI: 27.4–33.7)] and Madrid [9.2 (95% CI: 7.5–10.9)], but not in adjusted NOR. After adjusting for various confounder variables, the point estimate of OL was higher in Barcelona [5.8 (95% CI: 3.3–9.2)] than in Madrid [1.9 (95% CI: 0.5–4.9)]. Finally, adjusted FOR, NOR and OL in the two cities pooled were 0.7 per 100 py

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the community cohort of young heroin users: Barcelona and Madrid, 2001–2006

	Barcelona		Madrid		Total		p*
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Age (years)							0.000
18–25	194	53.3	140	32.8	334	42.2	
26–30	170	46.7	287	67.2	457	57.8	
Sex							0.406
Men	251	68.0	306	71.7	557	70.4	
Women	113	31.0	121	28.3	234	29.6	
Educational level							0.043
Primary or lower	124	34.1	175	41.1	299	37.8	
Secondary	240	65.9	251	58.9	491	62.2	
Treatment at baseline							0.513
Yes	185	51.1	225	53.4	410	52.4	
No	177	48.9	196	46.6	373	47.6	
Drug injection status at baseline							0.000
Ever-injector	293	80.5	278	65.1	571	72.2	
Never-injector	71	19.5	149	34.9	220	27.8	

* Differences between Madrid and Barcelona.

(95% CI: 0.4–1.1), 15.8 per 100 py (95% CI: 14.3–17.6) and 4.2% (95% CI: 2.5–6.5), respectively.

When we stratified heroin users according to the presence or absence of changes in administration route during the study period, we observed differences in the lethality ratio between groups. None of the heroin users that were non-injectors at baseline and remained non-injectors until the end of follow-up had died, whereas the mortality rates among participants who had changed the administration route or were injectors throughout the follow-up period were 2.0 per 100 py (95% CI: 0.6–4.5) and 1.4 per 100 py (95% CI: 0.5–2.8), respectively. NOR showed the greatest differences between groups: participants who were injectors from baseline to the end of follow-up had higher mortality rates [38.9 per 100 py (95% CI: 32.5–45.4)] than those who changed administration route during follow-up [23.4 per 100 py (95% CI: 19.9–27.1)] or who had never injected up until the end of follow-up [2.3 per 100 py (95% CI: 1.2–3.8)] (table 3).

Discussion

This study allowed us to calculate OL (as a proportion) among young heroin users from Madrid and Barcelona. The adjusted OL was found to be 4.2% (i.e. out of 100 overdoses, 4 resulted in death).

Table 2. Crude and adjusted FOR and NOR and crude and adjusted OL ratio among young heroin users: Barcelona and Madrid, 2001–2006

	Barcelona	Madrid	Total
Fatal opioid overdoses	12	5	17
Person-years	1,175	1,261	2,435
FOR and 95% CI (per 100 py)	1.0 (0.6–1.7)	0.4 (0.2–0.9)	0.7 (0.4–1.1)
Adjusted FOR ¹	1.1 (0.6–1.8)	0.3 (0.1–0.7)	0.7 (0.4–1.1)
Non-fatal opioid overdose	255	103	358
Person-years	839	1,127	1,966
NOR and 95% CI (per 100 py)	30.4 (27.4–33.7)	9.2 (7.5–10.9)	18.2 (16.6–20.0)
Adjusted NOR ¹	18.3 (15.8–20.9)	13.7 (11.8–15.8)	15.9 (14.3–17.6)
OL and 95% CI ¹ , %	3.3 (1.8–5.4)	4.3 (1.6–8.9)	3.7 (2.2–5.7)
Adjusted OL ²	5.8 (3.3–9.2)	1.9 (0.5–4.9)	4.2 (2.6–6.5)

¹ OL = [FOR/(FOR + NOR)] × 100. 95% CI was estimated using Bayesian models (see Methods). ² Adjusted for age, sex, educational level, treatment at baseline, drug injection status at baseline and city of residence.

Table 3. FOR and NOR, and OL ratio among young heroin users according to administration route during follow up: Barcelona and Madrid, 2001–2006

Route of administration	Injectors during follow-up	Non-injectors during follow-up	Changes in administration route during follow-up ²
Individuals, n	81	167	157
Fatal opioid overdose, n	4	0	5
Person-years	208	429	380
FOR and 95% CI (per 100 py)	2.0 (0.6–4.5)	–	1.4 (0.5–2.8)
Non-fatal opioid overdose, n	87	12	123
Person-years	224	536	526
NOR and 95% CI (per 100 py)	38.9 (32.5–45.4)	2.3 (1.2–3.8)	23.4 (19.9–27.1)
OL and 95% CI ¹ , %	4.9 (1.6–10.4)	–	5.4 (2.1–11.1)

¹ OL = [FOR/(FOR + NOR)] × 100. 95% CI was estimated using Bayesian models (see Methods). ² It was considered that the route of heroin administration changed if the participant was not a heroin injector at baseline and injected such drug at least once during follow-up or if he was a heroin injector at baseline and never injected this drug during follow-up. The individual average follow-up period for changes in administration route was 3.18 years (NOR) and 2.51 years (FOR).

This is the first study that examines OL using data from a prospective community cohort of young heroin users. Previously, one published study was based on a non-community cohort (treatment patients) [17], and another two combined different sources of information on fatal and non-fatal overdoses [12, 16]. Moreover, our statistical analysis has been conducted using the most appropriate methods, including Bayesian methods for obtaining the proportion of lethality and its credibility intervals.

However, the study has also some limitations. (1) The most important limitation is the sample size, although the overall OL, FOR and NOR estimations are robust and the differences in the point estimate of OL between cities suggest some possible explanations, which must be confirmed in further studies. (2) The study linked the overall cohort to the national mortality register; thus, emigrants who died abroad could have resulted in underestimation of the OL. Nevertheless, given the low rate of emigration during the study period, this effect can be considered negligible. (3) It is very difficult to evaluate how representative the sample is, and if it is equally representative in both cities; while the same protocol was followed in Barcelona and Madrid, differences were observed in some characteristics of the participants in each city, and we cannot rule out possible effects on recruitment. To alleviate this potential problem, the adjusted analyses were performed after stratification by city and included city as an independent variable. (4) Self-reports of drug use could lead to an information bias, although studies have shown that self-reported drug use is both accurate and reliable [24, 25].

(5) We assumed that the annual FOR was constant during the study period, which is supported by the lack of statistical differences in the NOR between participants at baseline and those with updated information during follow-up. (6) Unfortunately, the inclusion of more independent variables in the models was not statistically possible due to the low number of deaths observed and consequent residual confounding due to uncontrolled factors such as depression [26] is possible; nevertheless, analyses were adjusted by the main sociodemographic factors and by the route of drug administration. (7) Some people classified at baseline as never having injected could have started injecting during follow-up without being detected [27]. Moreover, a selection bias with greater loss to follow-up among injectors may lead to overestimation of the FOR and OL, while greater loss among non-injectors or those who stop injecting or using illicit opioids would have the opposite effect. Other studies have also failed to avoid these potential sources of bias.

The opioid OL in this population of young heroin users was similar to that previously estimated in other locations. Published data, although scarce, describe OL ratios ranging from 3.1 to 5% [12, 16, 17]. In our study, we found a crude and adjusted lethality of 3.7 and 4.2%, respectively, and given that opioid overdose is preventable and easily reversible with adequate care and treatment [14], this percentage seems unacceptably high. This is probably explained by the fact that in Spain in general [19], and in Barcelona in particular, most young heroin users have been found to have insufficient knowledge and skills about how to prevent or reverse an opioid overdose. In Barcelona in 2008–2009, 35.9% of injected heroin users could not identify any adequate harm reduction action in case of witnessing an overdose, and 61.1% could identify only one. Calling an emergency service and giving first aid were the most frequently mentioned adequate actions and only 3.8% cited naloxone administration [28]. In addition, the context of heroin use in Barcelona and Madrid could contribute to this lethality. The proportion of participants in both cities that used drugs in solitary as the most frequent context of use was high and very similar (32.1% in Barcelona and 29.7% in Madrid). Regardless, the most common places of consumption in both Barcelona and Madrid were open-air drug scenes, streets or parks (64.8% in Barcelona and 57.2% in Madrid), where drug users are in the company of others [18]. In addition, specific, systematic programs aimed at preventing overdoses and their consequences were not widespread during the study period. This is important because the high rates we observed of both NOR [18.2 per 100 py (95% CI: 16.6–20.0)] and FOR [0.7 per 100 py (95% CI: 0.4–1.1)] could be reduced by preventive practices [9]. The NOR rate obtained in this study was a more exact estimation than the previously reported annual prevalence of non-fatal opioid overdose [11, 13, 29]. At any rate, our results were coherent with previously published estimates, which range from 9 to 22% [11, 13, 29].

In our study, the crude OL estimates for Barcelona and Madrid showed a noticeable change after adjustment by potential confounders. Both age and route of drug administration were the most influential factors affecting the OL estimate. The higher number of both young participants and drug injectors in the Barcelona sample probably explains the increase in adjusted OL in Barcelona and the decrease in Madrid, with respect to the crude values. Nevertheless, even after adjustment, the OL is still remarkably high, especially in Barcelona, where other unmeasured factors may contribute to the risk of dangerous opioid overdose [10]. Although there were no statistically significant

differences in the adjusted OL between Madrid and Barcelona, possibly due to a lack of statistical power, the point estimate was clearly higher in Barcelona. As mentioned, the difference in OL between the two cities was not related to age, sex, educational level, treatment for drug dependence or drug injection status at baseline. Unfortunately, the limited sample size and the unmeasured variables precluded the inclusion of other individual adjustment variables, such as the concurrent use of other drugs at the moment of the overdose, or other variables that could change during follow-up [10, 27]. Furthermore, some structural or contextual factors, such as the availability of harm-reduction interventions aimed at reducing the OL might help to explain the difference between Barcelona and Madrid. Nevertheless, during the study period neither city had a naloxone distribution program, nor were there systematic measures for overdose prevention. On the other hand, both cities had supervised injection facilities, and although there are more of these facilities in Barcelona, it seems unlikely that this would have an impact on mortality [30]. We observed no difference between the two cities in the prevalence of drug use in solitary [18].

Our results showed a high percentage of fatal overdoses among young heroin users (aged 18–30 years) who had changed their injection status during the follow-up period, which suggests that this specific group deserves special attention. These high percentages could be addressed with specific training in measures aimed at avoiding the consequences of opioid overdose after it has occurred, such as injecting in places where others can help them in case of overdose, or never injecting in solitary. Furthermore, it is likely that, when witnessing an opioid overdose, long-term drug injectors know better how to act than non-injectors or inexperienced drug injectors, which is also the case with preventive behaviours for avoiding overdoses and death after overdose [19]. Moreover, it is important to be aware that the use of non-injecting routes of opioid administration (smoking, sniffing or swallowing) does not completely eliminate the risk of overdose [6, 31]. Opioid overdoses may become more lethal in the initial period after beginning drug injection when the tolerance to opioids is thought to be low, as is also the case after a period of abstinence [9]. In fact, the lethality ratio among individuals who were injectors at both baseline and follow-up was similar to that among those who changed the administration route, and there were no deaths among non-injectors at either time point. Finally, a recent study [32] suggests that the time window between onset of illicit drug use and fatal overdose is generally shorter for women than for men. Further studies with larger sample sizes are required to analyse the role of gender in opioid lethality.

In conclusion, we observed high lethality from opioid overdose among young heroin users, similar to that observed in other studies. This high lethality, especially in young heroin users, highlights the need to implement programs to reduce the risk of mortality in case of opioid overdose. Those programs could include, for example, supervised drug consumption facilities, training heroin users in overdose care, or distributing naloxone to this group or their relatives. It is also very important that these programs target non-injecting heroin or opioid users, especially those with a high risk of transition to injection.

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References

- 1 UNODC: World Drug Report 2013 (Sales N. E.13.XI.6). New York, United Nations Publication, 2013.
- 2 Degenhardt L, Bucello C, Mathers B, Briegleb C, Ali H, Hickman M, et al: Mortality among regular or dependent users of heroin and other opioids: a systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies. *Addiction* 2011;106:32–51.
- 3 Davoli M, Perucci CA, Rapiti E, Bargagli AM, D'Ippoliti D, Forastiere F, et al: A persistent rise in mortality among injection drug users in Rome, 1980 through 1992. *Am J Public Health* 1997;87:851–853.
- 4 Bargagli AM, Hickman M, Davoli M, Perucci CA, Schifano P, Buster M, et al: Drug-related mortality and its impact on adult mortality in eight European countries. *Eur J Public Health* 2006;16:198–202.
- 5 Orti RM, Domingo-Salvany A, Munoz A, Macfarlane D, Suelves JM, Anto JM: Mortality trends in a cohort of opiate addicts, Catalonia, Spain. *Int J Epidemiol* 1996;25:545–553.
- 6 Brugal MT, Domingo-Salvany A, Puig R, Barrio G, Garcia de Olalla P, de la Fuente L: Evaluating the impact of methadone maintenance programmes on mortality due to overdose and aids in a cohort of heroin users in Spain. *Addiction* 2005;100:981–989.
- 7 Barrio AG, Oliva J, Bravo MJ, Mateo SD, Domingo-Salvany A: Estimating the prevalence of drug injection using a multiplier method based on a register of new HIV diagnoses. *Eur J Public Health* 2011;21:646–648.
- 8 Sanchez-Niubo A, Fortiana J, Barrio G, Suelves JM, Correa JF, Domingo-Salvany A: Problematic heroin use incidence trends in Spain. *Addiction* 2009;104:248–255.
- 9 Preventing Overdose Deaths in Europe. Lisbon, EMCDDA, 2013. http://www.salledeconsommation.fr/_media/emcdda-2013-preventing-overdose-deaths.pdf.
- 10 Waal H, Gossop M: Making sense of differing overdose mortality: contributions to improved understanding of European patterns. *Eur Addict Res* 2014;20:8–15.
- 11 Brugal MT, Barrio G, De LF, Regidor E, Royuela L, Suelves JM: Factors associated with non-fatal heroin overdose: assessing the effect of frequency and route of heroin administration. *Addiction* 2002;97:319–327.
- 12 Darke S, Ross J, Hall W: Overdose among heroin users in Sydney, Australia. II. Responses to overdose. *Addiction* 1996;91:413–417.
- 13 Gossop M, Griffiths P, Powis B, Williamson S, Strang J: Frequency of non-fatal heroin overdose: survey of heroin users recruited in non-clinical settings. *BMJ* 1996;313:402. Sporer KA: Strategies for preventing heroin overdose. *BMJ* 2003;326:442–444.
- 14 Sporer KA: Acute heroin overdose. *Ann Intern Med* 1999;130:584–590.
- 15 Darke S, Mattick RP, Degenhardt L: The ratio of non-fatal to fatal heroin overdose. *Addiction* 2003;98:1169–1171.
- 16 Neale J: A response to Darke et al, 'The ratio of non-fatal to fatal heroin overdose'. *Addiction* 2003;98:1171.
- 17 De la Fuente L, Brugal Puig MT, Ballesta GR, Bravo Poetela MJ, Barrio AG, Domingo SA, et al: Cohort study methodology of the ITINERE Project on heroin users in three Spanish cities and main characteristics of the participants (in Spanish). *Rev Esp Salud Publica* 2005;79:475–491.
- 18 Neira-Leon M, Barrio G, Bravo MJ, Brugal MT, de la FL, Domingo-Salvany A, et al: Infrequent opioid overdose risk reduction behaviours among young adult heroin users in cities with wide coverage of HIV prevention programmes. *Int J Drug Policy* 2011;22:16–25.
- 19 Santos S, Molist G, Barrio G, Pulido J, Bravo MJ, Fernandez-Cuenca R, et al: Classification of illicit drug-induced deaths in Spain: toward the adoption of the European standard criteria (in Spanish). *Gac Sanit* 2010;24:309–313.
- 20 Gotsens M, Mari-Dell'Olmo M, Rodríguez-Sanz M, Martos D, Espelt A, Pérez G, et al: Validation of the underlying cause of death in medicolegal deaths (in Spanish). *Rev Esp Salud Publica* 2011;85:173–184.
- 21 Gelman A, Carlin J, Stern H, Rubin D: Bayesian data analysis. Boca Raton, Chapman & Hall/CRC, 2004.
- 22 De la Fuente L, Barrio G, Royuela L, Bravo MJ: The transition from injecting to smoking heroin in three Spanish cities. The Spanish Group for the Study of the Route of Heroin Administration. *Addiction* 1997;92:1749–1763.
- 23 Fendrich M, Mackesy-Amity ME, Wislar JS, Goldstein P: The reliability and consistency of drug reporting in ethnographic samples. *NIDA Res Monogr* 1997;167:81–107.
- 24 Napper LE, Fisher DG, Johnson ME, Wood MM: The reliability and validity of drug users' self reports of amphetamine use among primarily heroin and cocaine users. *Addict Behav* 2010;35:350.
- 25 Chahua M, Sordo L, Barrio G, Domingo-Salvany A, Brugal MT, Molist G, et al: Non-fatal opioid overdose and major depression among street-recruited young heroin users. *Eur Addict Res* 2014;20:1–7.
- 26 Darke S, Zador D: Fatal heroin 'overdose': a review. *Addiction* 1996;91:1765–1772.
- 27 Sarasa-Renedo A, Espelt A, Folch C, Vecino C, Majó X, Castellano Y, et al: Overdose prevention in injecting opioid users: the role of substance abuse treatment and training programs. *Gac Sanit* 2014;28:146–154.
- 28 Darke S, Ross J, Hall W: Overdose among heroin users in Sydney, Australia. I. Prevalence and correlates of non-fatal overdose. *Addiction* 1996;91:405–411.
- 29 Bravo MJ, Royuela L, De la Fuente L, Brugal MT, Barrio G, Domingo-Salvany A: Use of supervised injection facilities and injection risk behaviours among young drug injectors. *Addiction* 2009;104:614–619.
- 30 Darke S, Ross J: Fatal heroin overdoses resulting from non-injecting routes of administration, NSW, Australia, 1992–1996. *Addiction* 2000;95:569–573.
- 31 Origer A, Lopes da Costa S, Baumann M: Opiate- and cocaine-related fatal overdoses in Luxembourg from 1985 to 2011: a study on gender differences. *Eur Addict Res* 2014;20:87–93.